

Mass Spectral Studies on Heterocyclic Compounds. Part-I. Fragmentation of some Fluorine containing Indole Derivatives under Electron Impact

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The fragmentation pathways of 5-/6-fluoro-2-(4'-fluorophenyl)indoles, 5-fluoro-2-(4'-fluorophenyl)-3-(*N,N*-dimethylglyoxylamido)indole, 5-fluoro-2-(4'-fluorophenyl)-3-(β -morpholinoethyl)indole and 5-fluoro-3-(4'-fluorophenylimino)-1-piperidino-methylindol-2-one have been studied. Structural assignments have been made for the major fragments, and the pathways leading to their formation have been postulated by the recognition of the appropriate metastable peaks and doubly charged ions.

IN recent years, mass spectrometric studies have been used in various aspects of biochemistry¹⁻³. The mass spectra of several indoles and indole derivatives have been discussed by a number of workers⁴⁻¹⁰. Some Russian workers⁶ have reported the mass fragmentation pathways of some phenylindoles.

Nonavailability of the literature on 2-phenylindole derivatives coupled with their use in the field of medicine and biochemistry, have prompted us to investigate the fragmentation pathways of some fluorine containing 2-phenylindole derivatives.

Experimental

The synthesis of 5-/6-fluoro-2-(4'-fluorophenyl)indoles, 5-fluoro-2-(4'-fluorophenyl)-3-(*N,N*-dimethylglyoxylamido)indole, 5-fluoro-2-(4'-fluorophenyl)-3-(β -morpholinoethyl)indole and 5-fluoro-3-(4'-fluorophenylimino)-1-piperidinomethylindol-2-one have earlier been reported from this laboratory¹¹⁻¹⁴. The mass spectra were recorded on a CEC 21-110B mass spectrometer, operating at an ionisation potential of 70 eV. The source temperature was maintained at 200-300°, depending upon the volatility of the compound.

Results and Discussion

Scheme 1: The mass spectral fragmentations of 5-fluoro-2-(4'-fluorophenyl)indole and 6-fluoro-2-(4'-fluorophenyl)indole are almost identical. The mass fragmentation of 6-fluoro-2-(4'-fluorophenyl)indole is shown in Scheme 1 and its molecular ion peak is the base peak (m/e 229).

In the first path, the molecular ion 1 eliminates readily one H radical to yield ion 2 (m/e 228, r.i. 7.0) and in the second path, it eliminates neutral HCN with rearrangement to cation radical 3 (m/e 202, r.i. 2.3). The latter path has been confirmed on the

basis of observed metastable peak at m/e 178.7 (229 \rightarrow 202). Ion 3 readily eliminates one H radical to give more stable cation 4 (m/e 201, r.i. 13.9). This observation is in harmony with the results of previous workers^{1,5}. Ion 3 can also produce cation

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

radical 5 (m/e 108, r.i. 12.75). After elimination of neutral HCN molecule, cation 2 produces cation 4. Cation 4 on further decomposition yields cation 6 (m/e 107, r.i. 8.4). Ions 5 and 6 rearrange into tropylium ions, which are more stable due to increased degree of conjugation. Other lower fragmentations are in accordance with characteristic

fragmentations of the corresponding hydrocarbons^{10, 17}.

Scheme 2: The mass fragmentation pathways of 5-fluoro-2-(4'-fluorophenyl)-3-(*N,N*-dimethylglyoxylamido)indole are shown in Scheme 2. The parent peak is indistinguishable. The proposed molecular ion 1 gives base peak at *m/e* 256 on breaking of C—C bond (β -to nitrogen of dimethylamino group). This cation 3 further loses one formyl radical producing cation radical 4 (*m/e* 227, r.i. 5.47), which may rearrange to cation 5 (*m/e* 201, r.i. 13.2) after elimination of cyanide radical. The molecular ion 1 also produces cation radical 2 (*m/e* 257, r.i. 17.4). Ion 2 eliminates one formaldehyde unit and gives cation radical 4. Ion 5 further decomposes as in Scheme 1. Ions 2 and 3 may be stabilised due to their rearrangement into quinolinium type of structures¹⁸.

Scheme 3: Scheme 3 shows the mass fragmentation pattern of 5-fluoro-2-(4'-fluorophenyl)-3-(β -morpholinoethyl)indole. The molecular ion 1 (*m/e* 342, r.i. 6.48) readily breaks at β -carbon atom of alkyl

Scheme 3

Scheme 4

chain and produces cation 2 (*m/e* 242, r.i. 7.0) and morpholinomethyl radical at *m/e* 100. It is interesting to note that morpholinomethyl radical constitutes base peak for this mass spectrum. Cation 2 gives cation radical 3 (*m/e* 229, r.i. 6.83) after elimination of one CH unit. The molecular ion 1 may also produce cation radical 4 (*m/e* 340, r.i. 3.1),

which further rearranges¹⁹⁻²¹ to cation 5 (*m/e* 240, r.i. 4.69) after elimination of morpholinomethyl radical. Further, decompositions of ion 3 are identical as in Scheme 1.

Scheme 4: The different fragments of 5-fluoro-3-(4'-fluorophenylimino)-1-piperidinomethylindol-2-one are represented in Scheme 4. The molecular ion at *m/e* 355 is of very low abundance and after elimination of piperidinomethyl radical (*m/e* 98, r.i. 100%, base peak) produces cation 2 (*m/e* 257, r.i. 6.05). Cation 2 further gives cation 7 (*m/e* 229) after elimination of one neutral CO molecule. Cation 7 further decomposes into ion 9 (*m/e* 121) and 10 (*m/e* 108, r.i. 5.72). The formation of cation 5 (*m/e* 243, r.i. 12.2) from the molecular ion 1 is possible in stepwise fragmentations via ion 3 (*m/e* 272). The stability of cation 5 may be due to its rearrangement into quinazolinium cation, which in turn decomposes into cations 8 (*m/e* 122, r.i. 4.3) and 9 (*m/e* 121, r.i. 3.2). The cation radical 3 may also produce ion 4 (*m/e* 258, r.i. 4.4), which in turn eliminates one CO molecule and gives rise to ion 6 (*m/e* 230, r.i. 8.32). Ion 6 further decomposes into ions 8 and 9. Ions 8 and 9, after elimination of HCN and cyanide radical, respectively, produce fluorobenzene cation 11 (*m/e* 95, r.i. 32.1).

Conclusion: In case of 5-/6-fluoro-2-(4'-fluorophenyl)indoles, it has been observed that 2-fluoroaryl substituent plays an important role in determining the fragmentation pathways of substituted indoles. The presence of a 2-fluoroaryl substituent in a number of ions and the formation of substituted fluorene type of compounds (Scheme 1) under electron impact indicates that the bond at 2-position of the indole ring is considerably stronger due to high degree of conjugation between indole and 2-phenyl ring, and is, therefore, not very easily broken. It may be worthwhile to consider the 2-fluoroaryl group as an additive part of indole molecule instead of as a simple substituent.

The decomposition products of 3-substituted derivatives of 2-phenylindoles involve the opening of β -bond (to the aromatic ring) of the substituents in 3-position and a rearrangement to the quinolinium type of structures as is observed in case of 2-methylindoles and 2-unsubstituted indoles. Furthermore, the stability of M^+ is decreased due to the presence of 2-phenyl substituents.

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